

Table S1. Color card of the colors referred to in this study. These color names were designated following the color nomenclatural code for description works of specimens in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM) (Yang 2023).

No.	Sample	Color Name		Color Code	Note
		Chinese	English		
\		猫鼬褐色	mongoose brown	#B5A284	Designated in Yang (2023)
39		烟灰色	smoke gray	#BCC6C8	Designated in this study
40		咖啡红色	coffee red	#7B5B4E	Designated in this study
41		燧石褐色	flint brown	#736960	Designated in this study
42		煤蓝色	coal blue	#40474D	Designated in this study
43		暗黑色	dull black	#0B0C0E	Designated in this study
44		西梅紫色	prune violet	#615074	Designated in this study
45		夜蓝色	night blue	#525A88	Designated in this study
46		暗薰衣草紫	dull lavender	#75647A	Designated in this study
47		棉籽灰色	cottonseed gray	#BEC0BB	Designated in this study
48		浓灰色	strong gray	#9D9D9D	Designated in this study
49		草木灰褐色	wood-ash brown	#A0968A	Designated in this study
50		深草黄色	dark thatch yellow	#CDC591	Designated in this study
51		海藻褐色	kelp brown	#ACA47E	Designated in this study
52		燕麦橙色	oat orange	#DFCE7E	Designated in this study
53		麦粒褐色	barleycorn brown	#9D8F59	Designated in this study
54		龙猫灰色	chinchilla gray	#7F7E80	Designated in this study
55		驼褐色	camel brown	#CDC196	Designated in this study
56		稻草褐色	straw brown	#C4B179	Designated in this study